

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF BLENDED LEARNING MODALITY (BLM) ON GRADE 6 STUDENTS' ENGAGEMENT AND PERFORMANCE: A LOOK THROUGH THE LENS OF SCHOOL LEADERS

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ABSTRACT

Blended learning, a pedagogical approach combining online and offline learning activities, has gained momentum in recent years. While its potential benefits are widely acknowledged, its successful implementation hinges on educator perceptions and practices. This study explored teachers and school administrators' perceptions of blended learning modality in San Jorge District. With the utilization of quantitative research method and a survey questionnaire, the survey found that both groups expressed positive views on blended learning, especially for its contribution to health protocols and student interaction. They favored a comprehensive model combining online, modular, and traditional learning with potential TV/Radio programs. However, some uncertainty remained regarding whether blended learning effectively covers all educational aspects. Additionally, administrators expressed concerns about managing blended learning assessments. The survey results identified a need for increased professional development opportunities, particularly at the district, division, and national levels, for both teachers and administrators. While student performance was strong, the survey design couldn't definitively link it to blended learning. Further research is recommended. Interestingly, there was high agreement between teachers and administrators on blended learning implementation, suggesting a shared understanding. Additionally, teachers' years of experience, regional in-service training, and attitude towards blended learning showed a weak to moderate correlation with their perception of blended learning modality implementation level. For school administrators, their

attitude toward blended learning and their division and regional level of relevant in-service training influenced their perception of BLM implementation. Thus, the study highlighted the potential of blended learning while pinpointing areas for improvement. Increased professional development, addressing concerns about educational coverage, and further research on student achievement are crucial for successful long-term implementation.

Keywords: *Academic Performance, Blended Learning Modality (BLM), Grade 6 Students, Student Engagement, Student Performance, School Leader Perspective*

INTRODUCTION

The global emergence of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in early 2020 severely disrupted educational systems worldwide. Traditional schools, vital hubs for intellectual and social interaction, were forced to close temporarily to comply with social distancing measures. This compelled educational institutions globally to transition to alternative learning modalities, moving away from conventional physical classrooms. Among these, blended learning became increasingly prevalent. As defined by Adigun et al. (2025), blended learning is a flexible approach that combines computer-mediated and face-to-face instructional activities, offering both synchronous and asynchronous learning opportunities. Given the unfamiliarity of this approach for both students and teachers, it remains crucial to assess its efficacy (Crawford et al., 2020).

In response to the pandemic's impact, many countries devised strategies to ensure the continuity of education and mitigate learning loss. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) during the 2020–2021 school year, a period marked by the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic. The BE-LCP comprises a comprehensive set of educational interventions designed to address the challenges faced by basic education due to school closures and the shift to remote learning. The plan mandated the exclusive use of distance learning modalities, replacing the face-to-face classroom setting (Department of Education, 2020).

Despite the advantages of distance learning in maintaining educational delivery during the pandemic, it introduced significant challenges for schools and their stakeholders, particularly teachers, students, and parents. Notable among these challenges were the parents' difficulty in supporting their children's education at home, the isolation experienced by students due to limited physical and social interaction, and the teachers' unpreparedness to manage the modularized learning environment. Furthermore, educators expressed concerns about the potential for students to underperform in an unfamiliar and unprepared learning setting (Schleicher, 2020).

Recognizing these challenges, the DepEd advocated for the gradual reintroduction of in-person instruction. The government approved the pilot implementation of face-to-

face classes in selected public and private schools in low-risk areas on September 20, 2021. Subsequently, the DepEd and the Department of Health (DOH) issued Joint Memorandum Circular No. 01, Series of 2021, on September 27, 2021, titled "Operational Guidelines on the Implementation of Limited Face-to-Face Learning Modality." These guidelines outline the mechanisms and standards for safely resuming face-to-face classes, with a phased approach encompassing pilot, expanded, and full implementation stages (Department of Health, 2021).

The pilot implementation, conducted from November 15 to December 17, 2021, in 284 schools across the country, demonstrated that a safe transition to in-person instruction was feasible. This success paved the way for the provisions outlined in Department of Education Order No. 34, Series of 2022, which facilitated preparations for the full resumption of five-day in-person classes, commencing on November 2, 2022. In the Schools Division of Samar, specifically within the District of San Jorge, schools reopened on August 22, 2022, utilizing a blended learning modality (BLM). This approach combines face-to-face or in-person learning with various forms of distance learning, including online, modular, and broadcast-based instruction (Department of Education, 2022).

The implementation of BLM during the 2022-2023 school year is anticipated to reignite students' academic engagement, which is crucial for improving academic performance. Academic engagement encompasses the attention, curiosity, interest, optimism, and passion students exhibit in the learning process. This aspect of education was significantly challenged during the period of modular distance learning adopted in response to the pandemic. Thus, the transition to BLM is seen as a strategic move to harness the boomerang principle in education—suggesting that the more effort invested in motivating students to remain engaged, the greater the likelihood that they will reciprocate, become involved, and progress in their learning (Alghanmi & Nyazi, 2022).

The use of BLM is not only a response to the challenges posed by the pandemic but also an effort by the education sector to address potential gaps in students' academic performance. Academic performance is a critical indicator of educational success, as it plays a vital role in producing quality graduates who will contribute to the nation's growth and development. It serves as tangible evidence of learning outcomes and is often assessed using both cognitive and non-cognitive measures, such as personality tests, attitudinal assessments, and aptitude evaluations. While factors like study habits and attitudes are frequently examined as determinants of academic performance, less attention has been given to understanding the impact of specific learning delivery modalities, such as BLM, on student achievement (Wang & Degol, 2017).

Despite the widespread use of BLM in other countries, it remains relatively novel in the Philippines, where traditional in-person instruction has long been the norm. This novelty underscores the necessity of assessing BLM's impact on students' academic performance. In the District of San Jorge, which was tasked with implementing BLM during the 2022-2023 school year, this study aims to evaluate how this instructional

modality has affected the academic performance of Grade 6 students, as perceived by teachers and school administrators.

Research Questions

This study assessed the perceptions of the teachers and school administrators on the impact of blended learning modality (BLM) on the academic performance of Grade 6 students of the District of San Jorge, Schools Division of Samar, during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of the following variates:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2 civil status;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 gross monthly family income;
 - 1.5 number of years in teaching;
 - 1.6 number of relevant in-service training;
 - 1.7 performance rating based on the latest IPCRF; and
 - 1.8 attitude toward blended learning modality?
2. What is the profile of the school administrator-respondents in terms of the following variates:
 - 2.1 age and sex;
 - 2.2 civil status;
 - 2.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 2.4 gross monthly family income;
 - 2.5 number of years as school administrator;
 - 2.6 number of relevant in-service training;
 - 2.7 performance rating based on the latest OPCRF; and
 - 2.8 attitude toward blended learning modality?
3. What is the level of implementation of blended learning modality as perceived by the teacher- and school administrator-respondents in terms of the foregoing areas:
 - 3.1 course management;
 - 3.2 interaction;
 - 3.3 performance; and
 - 3.4 satisfaction?
4. Is there a significant difference in the perceptions of the teacher- and school administrator-respondents as regards to the level of implementation of blended learning modality in terms of the identified areas?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perceptions of the teacher- and school administrator-respondents as regards to the level of implementation of blended learning modality in terms of the identified areas and the following:
 - 5.1 teacher-related variates; and
 - 5.2 school administrator-respondents?
6. What is the academic performance of the students based on their final grades in the various learning areas?

7. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of the students in the various learning areas and the respondents' perceptions on the level of implementation of blended learning modality along with some areas?

8. What intervention program may be implemented based on the findings of the study?

Locale of the Study

Figure 1
The Map Showing the Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the District of San Jorge, Schools Division of Samar. This district is geographically located in the Municipality of San Jorge, one of the municipalities in the Province of Samar. The said municipality is a landlocked municipality with a land area of 241.20 square kilometers which constitutes about 3.99% of Samar's total land area. Based on the 2020 census of population by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), its population was estimated at 17,579 people representing about 2.22% percent of the total population of the Province of Samar or 0.39% of the overall population of Eastern Visayas (Philippine Atlas Online, 2022, p 1).

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design to investigate the perceptions of teachers and school administrators regarding the impact of the Blended Learning Modality (BLM) on the academic performance of Grade 6 students in the District of San Jorge, Schools Division of Samar. The methodology involved profiling teacher- and school administrator-respondents based on various demographic and professional characteristics, assessing their attitudes toward BLM, and evaluating their perceptions on the level of BLM implementation across areas like course management, interaction, performance, and satisfaction. Additionally, students' academic performance was assessed using their final grades. For instrumentation, two sets of questionnaires, with items adapted from standard sources (Ayasrah et al., 2022; Zeqiri et al., 2020), were used to gather data on respondent profiles, attitudes, and perceptions of BLM implementation. Student report cards served as the primary document for assessing academic performance. The questionnaires underwent expert validation by the research adviser and oral defense panel members to ensure content validity. Sampling involved a 100% response rate from a total enumeration of 147 teachers and 35 school administrators from the district. For data gathering, the researcher secured necessary permissions from school authorities before personally distributing and retrieving questionnaires across various elementary schools, including hard-to-access locations. Documentary analysis of student report cards was conducted with strict adherence to data privacy regulations. Comparative and correlation analyses were conducted to determine differences in perceptions and relationships between variables, respectively. Data normality was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test, and both descriptive and inferential statistical tools—including Frequency Count, Percentage, Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, t-Test, Spearman's Rank Order Coefficient of Correlation, Fisher's t-Test, Mann-Whitney U-Test, Chi-Square Test, and Cramer's V-Test—were utilized for comprehensive data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. The data suggests that teachers in this sample are relatively young, with a majority falling within the age range of 27–31 years old (25.85%) and 32–36 years old

(18.37%). There is also a clear skew towards female teachers in the sample, where there are 114 female teachers compared to 33 male teachers. The median age of 36 years old implies that half the teachers are younger than 36 and half are older. However, the mean absolute deviation (MAD) of 8.2245 years suggests the teachers' ages are fairly spread out.

2. The data on marital status reveals a clear trend towards marriage among the teacher-respondents. With a significant majority of 72.11% being married, it suggests that most teachers in this sample are partnered or married. However, there is also a substantial portion of single teachers, accounting for 25.17%. A small minority, merely 1.36% each, falls under the categories of separated and widowed.

3. The highest percentage of teacher-respondents (47.62%) are currently enrolled in graduate or masters' programs. This is followed by those with a bachelor's degree only (23.81%) and those who already have a graduate degree (16.33%). These findings suggest that a significant portion of teachers are seeking to further their education.

4. The income distribution among the teacher-respondents leans towards the Php 25,000 – 29,999 range, with 32.65% falling within this bracket. This is followed by a significant portion (25.17%) earning Php 50,000 and above. Another considerable group (23.13%) earns between Php 30,000 – 34,999.

5. The largest group of respondents (43.54%) has less than 3 years of teaching experience. This is followed by a substantial portion (25.17%) with 7-9 years of experience. While there are teachers with more experience (19.05% with 4-6 years and 12.24% with 10 years and above), the data suggests that a significant number of teachers are relatively new to the field.

6. The majority of teacher-respondents (64.63%) have participated in 6 or more school-level trainings. This is followed by a sizable group (21.77%) with 3-5 trainings, indicating a commitment to continued learning even among those with some experience. However, a smaller portion (13.61%) reported having less than 3 trainings, suggesting some variation in the level of professional development participation among the teachers surveyed.

7. The data on district-level professional development shows that a majority of teachers (68.03%) have participated in relatively few trainings (less than 3). However, there is also a good number of teachers (31.97%) who have participated in more trainings (3-5 or 6 or more). This indicates that some teachers are actively seeking out professional development opportunities.

8. The data on division-level professional development reveals that a substantial portion of teachers (48.30%) have not attended any division trainings. This is followed by a significant group (36.73%) with less than 3 trainings. While some teachers have participated in more (8.84% with 3-5 trainings and 6.12% with 6 or more trainings), overall, the data suggests that a large number of teachers would benefit from increased

opportunities for professional development at the division level.

9. The data on regional-level professional development shows a strong preference for less frequent attendance. The overwhelming majority of teachers (72.79%) have not participated in any regional trainings. There is a fair portion (25.17%) with minimal attendance (less than 3 trainings). Only a very small number (2.04%) have participated in 3-5 trainings, and there are none who have attended 6 or more regional trainings.

10. The data on national-level professional development reveals a significant gap in participation. A large majority of teachers (76.87%) have not attended any national trainings. While there is a portion (22.45%) who have participated in a small number (less than 3 trainings), it's a very small group. The fact that only one teacher attended 3-5 trainings and none attended 6 or more suggests a lack of widespread participation in national-level professional development opportunities.

11. The data on teacher performance evaluations leans towards positive results. The majority of teacher-respondents (80.95%) received a rating of "Very Satisfactory" (3.500-4.499) on their latest Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). This indicates that most teachers are meeting expectations and performing well. While a smaller portion (19.05%) received the highest rating of "Outstanding" (4.500-5.000).

12. The grand weighted mean for teacher-respondents attitude toward blended learning modality is 3.83 which falls within "agree". Thus, the data bodes well for the implementation of blended learning, as teachers generally have a positive attitude towards it. The highest weighted mean (4.37) falls within the "agree" range for the statement "BLM brings about greater commitment to health protocol and public health standards." This indicates that teachers believe blended learning can help maintain health protocols during these times. On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean (3.04) falls within the "undecided" range for the statement "BLM neglects many elements of the educational process." This suggests that teachers are unsure whether blended learning can adequately address all the necessary aspects of education.

13. The largest age group for school administrators is 52 years old and older, making up over a quarter (25.71%) of respondents. The second largest age group is a tie between 27–31-year-olds and 37–41-year-olds, each consisting of 20.00% of respondents. The third largest age group is another tie, with both 42–46-year-olds and 32–36-year-olds accounting for 14.29% of respondents each. Finally, the smallest age group is 47–51-year-olds, at only 5.71% of respondents. The average school administrator respondent is 41.60 years old, which is the mean age. The median age, representing the middle value, is 39.00 years old. There is a spread of ages around the mean as indicated by the mean absolute deviation (MAD) of 8.42 years. In other words, the average respondent is 41.6 years old, but half of the respondents are younger and older than 39 years old. The fact that the mean is larger than the median suggests that there may be a tail towards older ages. The mean absolute deviation (MAD) of 8.42 years shows that the ages are spread out around the mean by an average of 8.42 years.

Moreover, the survey had a higher number of female respondents (21) compared to male respondents (14).

14. The survey results show that a significant majority of school administrator-respondents are married, at 77.14%. Only 22.86% of respondents are single.

15. The highest percentage of school administrator respondents (48.57%) are with units in graduate programs. There are also 10 respondents (28.57%) who have a graduate degree. 2 respondents (5.71%) have a post-graduate degree, while 5 respondents (14.21%) only have a bachelor's degree. Only 1 respondent (2.86%) has post graduate degree.

16. The majority (40.00%) fall within the Php 30,000 – 34,999 income brackets, with another significant portion (34.29%) earning between Php 25,000 – 29,999. Only a small percentage (11.43%) reported incomes exceeding Php 50,000.

17. The survey results indicate that a majority of school administrator-respondents (60.00%) have a moderate level of experience, having served between 4 and 6 years in their roles. In contrast, there are fewer respondents at either end of the experience spectrum. While a significant portion (28.57% or 10 respondents) have extensive experience of 10 years or more, a smaller group (11.43% or 4 respondents) have only 3 years of experience or less.

18. The majority (65.71%, or 23 respondents) have participated in less than 3 school training sessions. While a significant portion (28.57% or 10 respondents) have attended 6 or more trainings, a smaller group (5.71% or 2 respondents) have participated in just 3-5 training sessions.

19. The survey results highlight a potential concern regarding the professional development of school administrators. A significant majority, a whopping 82.86% (29 respondents), have participated in very few district training sessions, with less than 3 under their belt. While a small portion, 11.43% (4 respondents), have participated in 3-5 training sessions, and an even smaller group, 5.71% (2 respondents), have attended 6 or more sessions.

20. The survey results expose a potential lack of engagement in division-level professional development for school administrators. The majority, a substantial 62.86% (22 respondents), have not attended any division trainings. While a somewhat smaller, but still significant, portion (28.57% or 10 respondents) have participated in a limited number of trainings (less than 3). Only a small group (8.57% or 3 respondents) have attended between 3 and 5 trainings, and there are no administrators who have participated in 6 or more division-level training sessions.

21. The survey results indicate a near-complete absence of participation in regional training programs for school administrators. A staggering majority, 94.29% (33 respondents), have not attended any regional trainings. There is minimal participation

beyond this, with only one respondent (2.86%) attending a limited number of trainings (less than 3) and another one attending a slightly higher number (3-5 trainings). Notably, no administrators reported attending 6 or more regional training sessions.

22. The survey results reveal a critical gap in professional development for school administrators. Absolutely none of the respondents (100%) have attended national training programs.

23. The survey results show positive performance evaluations for school administrators. The majority, a strong 57.14% (20 respondents), received the highest rating (4.50-5.00) which translates to "Outstanding" on their latest OPCR (Overall Performance Evaluation and Rating). This indicates a high level of achievement and performance across the board. While not achieving the top rating, a significant portion (42.86% or 15 respondents) still received a very positive rating (3.50-4.49) which translates to "Very Satisfactory" on their OPCR.

24. The grand weighted mean of 3.79 falls within the "agree" range, suggesting that most administrators see value in this approach. Specifically, administrators seem most enthusiastic about the potential of BLM to improve health and safety. The highest weighted mean (4.49, within the "agree" range) goes to the statement regarding BLM's contribution to better health protocols. On the other hand, there appears to be some uncertainty about neglecting educational elements with BLM. The lowest weighted mean (2.69) falls within the "undecided" range for the statement about BLM neglecting aspects of education. This suggests that some administrators may require more information or clarification on how BLM can effectively address the entire educational process.

25. The survey results show that teachers generally perceive blended learning as a positive approach along with course management, with a grand weighted mean of 3.93 falling within the "agree" range. This suggests that most teachers see blended learning as a helpful tool. Specifically, teachers seem most convinced of the overall benefit of blended learning modalities for managing and organizing learning. The highest weighted mean (4.20, within the "agree" range) goes to the statement regarding the suitability of various blended learning options (online, modular, TV/Radio, and face-to-face) for pandemic situations. While still positive, there appears to be slightly less agreement on the convenience of blended learning for assignments. The lowest weighted mean (3.77) falls within the "agree" range for the statement about arranging and grading assignments. This suggests that some teachers may find blended learning to require a bit more effort when it comes to managing assessments.

26. The survey results show a strong endorsement of blended learning's impact on interaction among teachers and students. The grand weighted mean of 4.11 falls within the "agree" range, signifying that most teachers perceive this modality as fostering positive interaction. Thus, the survey suggests that teachers believe blended learning creates a more interactive learning environment. The highest weighted mean is for the statement "Blended learning improves the communication and interaction between students and teachers" (4.15) which falls within agree range. Interestingly, even the

lowest weighted mean (4.00, within the "agree" range) suggests a positive perception. This statement focused on blended learning creating a user-friendly environment for the entire school community. While not quite as strong as the emphasis on improved student-teacher interaction, it still suggests teachers see blended learning as beneficial for overall communication and user experience within the school.

27. The grand weighted mean for the level of implementation of blended learning modality as perceived by the teacher-respondents along with performance is 3.76 which falls within agree range. This suggests that teachers generally perceive blended learning as having a positive impact on student performance. When delve deeper, the statement with the highest weighted mean (3.80, within "agree") highlights a specific aspect of blended learning that teachers find particularly beneficial. This statement focuses on the potential for improved grades when classes combine online learning, TV/ radio instruction, modular learning, and face-to-face interaction. This suggests that teachers see value in the comprehensive approach that blended learning offers. Interestingly, the statement with the lowest weighted mean (3.72, still within "agree") doesn't necessarily contradict the positive outlook. While it focuses on blended learning being the "best" way to improve performance, its weighted mean within the "agree" range indicates that teachers still see it as a valuable approach.

28. The survey results indicate that teachers are generally satisfied with the implementation of blended learning in their classrooms. The grand weighted mean of 3.63 falls within the "agree" range, suggesting that most teachers find the approach positive. The survey results offer a multifaceted perspective on teacher perceptions of blended learning. Teachers seem to favor a comprehensive approach to blended learning. The highest weighted mean (3.80 within "agree") is associated with a statement endorsing a combination of face-to-face instruction, online learning, modular learning, and TV/Radio instruction. This suggests that teachers see value in leveraging multiple methods within blended learning to create a well-rounded learning experience. However, there's also some room for improvement in terms of teacher satisfaction. The lowest weighted mean (3.51 within "agree") is associated with a statement comparing blended learning experiences to traditional classroom settings. While still positive, this score suggests that teacher satisfaction with blended learning may not be quite as high as with traditional methods. This might indicate areas where the implementation of blended learning could be improved to better meet teachers' needs and enhance their overall satisfaction.

29. The survey results reveal that school administrators hold a positive view of blended learning's impact along with course management, with a grand weighted mean of 4.00 falling within the "agree" range. This suggests that most administrators see blended learning as a helpful tool for organizing and delivering instruction effectively. The highest weighted mean (4.40, within "agree") goes to the statement highlighting the suitability of various blended learning modalities (online, modular, TV/Radio, and face-to-face) for pandemic situations. This suggests that administrators see blended learning as a way to adapt and manage learning effectively during challenging circumstances. There seems to be a slight reservation regarding the convenience of blended learning for assignments. The lowest weighted mean (3.74, within "agree") is associated with the

statement about arranging and grading assignments. While still positive, it suggests that administrators may perceive blended learning to require a bit more effort when it comes to managing assessments compared to traditional methods.

30. The survey results paint a positive picture of how school administrators perceive blended learning's impact on interaction within the school community. The grand weighted mean of 4.24 falls within the "agree" range, indicating that most administrators see blended learning as a positive force for communication and interaction. The highest weighted mean (4.29, within "agree") is associated with the statement highlighting improved communication and interaction between students and teachers. This suggests that administrators believe blended learning fosters a more engaging learning environment where students can connect more effectively with their instructors. Interestingly, even the lowest weighted mean (4.20, within "agree") reflects a positive outlook. This statement focused on blended learning creating a user-friendly environment for the entire school community. While not quite as strong as the emphasis on student-teacher interaction, it still suggests that administrators see blended learning as beneficial for overall communication and user experience within the school.

31. The survey results show that school administrators generally view blended learning as having a positive impact on student performance, although their perspective is cautiously optimistic. The overall grand weighted mean falls within the "agree" range (3.71), suggesting a general belief that blended learning can benefit student achievement. The highest weighted mean (3.74 within "agree") is for the statement about blended learning improving overall student performance across subjects. This suggests that administrators see potential for positive effects in various learning areas. On the other hand, the lowest weighted means (both 3.69 within "agree") are associated with statements about blended learning being the "best" way to improve performance or directly leading to better grades. While still positive, these scores indicate a touch of reservation. Administrators may acknowledge the potential benefits but might not see blended learning as a guaranteed solution or the single most effective approach.

32. The survey results regarding school administrator satisfaction with blended learning present a mixed picture. The grand weighted mean of 3.63 falls within the "agree" range, suggesting a general endorsement of blended learning's implementation. Administrators seem to favor a comprehensive blended learning approach. The highest weighted mean (3.83 within "agree") is associated with a statement endorsing a combination of face-to-face instruction, online learning, modular learning, and TV/Radio instruction. This suggests administrators see value in leveraging multiple methods within blended learning. However, satisfaction levels with blended learning experiences appear to be lower compared to traditional settings. The lowest weighted mean (3.44) falls within the "undecided" range for the statement about being more satisfied with blended learning compared to traditional classrooms. This is a significant shift from the "agree" range in other aspects.

33. The survey results suggest that there is not a significant difference in how teachers and school administrators view the implementation of blended learning across

the identified areas. This conclusion is based on the null hypothesis being accepted. The null hypothesis stated that there would be no difference in perceptions, and the high p-value (0.95, greater than the significance level of 0.05) supports this. This suggests that both groups share a common understanding of how blended learning is currently functioning within the schools.

34. The survey result shows three main variables: number of years in teaching (weak), regional level relevant in-service trainings (very weak), and attitude toward blended learning modality (moderate), with a significant correlation with the teachers' perception of the level of implementation of blended learning. While the remaining variables (age and sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, gross monthly family income, number of relevant in-service trainings along with school, district, division, and national level trainings, and performance rating based on the latest IPCRF) revealed no significant correlation with the teachers' perception of the level of implementation of blended learning.

35. This survey of school administrators identified three factors influencing their perception of how well blended learning is being implemented. The most influential factor, though with a weak correlation, was their attitude towards blended learning itself. Administrators with a more positive view perceived it as being implemented more effectively. The survey also revealed weak correlations with the level of relevant in-service training received. Interestingly, the correlation with regional training was even weaker than that with training provided at the division level. This suggests that current training programs, may not be strongly influencing administrator perception of blended learning implementation. While the remaining variables (age and sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, gross monthly family income, number of relevant in-service trainings along with school, district, and national level trainings, and performance rating based on the latest OPCRf) revealed no significant correlation with the school administrators' perception of the level of implementation of blended learning.

36. The survey results reveal a strong showing in academic performance among the student body. The majority of respondents (45.95%) achieved a general weighted average (GWA) between 80-84. This is followed by a substantial number of students (35.14%) with an even higher GWA between 85-89. Finally, a noteworthy group (18.92%) achieved an impressive GWA ranging from 90-95.

37. This survey investigated the relationship between teachers' perceptions of blended learning implementation and student academic performance across various learning areas. The researcher proposed a null hypothesis stating that there's no significant connection between these factors. The analysis resulted in a p-value of 0.056, which is greater than the commonly accepted significance level of 0.05. In simpler terms, the evidence was not strong enough to reject the null hypothesis. This means the survey did not find a statistically significant relationship between teachers' perceptions of blended learning and student academic performance. In other words, teachers' views on how well blended learning is being implemented were not necessarily reflected in student achievement.

38. This survey investigated the connection between how school administrators perceive blended learning implementation and student academic performance across different subjects. The researcher started with the assumption that there's no link (null hypothesis). The analysis resulted in a p-value of 0.112, which is higher than the standard significance level of 0.05. In simpler terms, the evidence wasn't strong enough to reject the null hypothesis. This means the survey did not find a statistically significant relationship between administrator perception of blended learning and student achievement in various subjects. In other words, administrators' views on how well blended learning is being implemented weren't necessarily reflected in student achievement.

Comparison Between the Perceptions of the Teacher-Respondents and School Administrator-Respondents as Regard to the Level of Implementation of Blended Learning Modality

Table 1 suggest that there is not a significant difference in how teachers and school administrators view the implementation of blended learning across the identified areas. This conclusion is based on the null hypothesis being accepted.

Table 1

Comparison Between the Perceptions of the Teacher-Respondents and School Administrator-Respondents as Regard to the Level of Implementation of Blended Learning Modality

Indicator	z-score	p-Value @ α=.05	Evaluation/ Decision
Level of Perceptions of the Teacher-Respondents as Regard to the Level of Implementation of Blended Learning Modality			
Level of Perceptions of the School Administrator-Respondents as Regard to the Level of Implementation of Blended Learning Modality	0.05534	0.95216	Not Significant/ Accept Ho.

The null hypothesis stated that there would be no difference in perceptions, and the high p-value (0.95, greater than the significance level of 0.05) supports this. In simpler terms, the data doesn't provide strong evidence that teachers and administrators have significantly different opinions on how blended learning is being implemented. This suggests that both groups share a common understanding of how blended learning is currently functioning within the schools.

This shared perspective could be a result of effective communication, participation in joint training programs, or similar experiences with blended learning implementation. However, it is important to acknowledge that the survey might not have captured all areas where potential discrepancies exist. A more detailed survey design or focus group discussions could provide deeper insights into any areas where teacher and administrator viewpoints diverge. Finally, even though there isn't a significant difference at present, it is important to continue monitoring perceptions over time. As blended learning evolves, ongoing evaluation can help ensure that both teachers and administrators feel supported and heard throughout the implementation process.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Teachers are relatively young, with most under 36 years old, and the majority are female. A significant number are pursuing further education through graduate studies, though many have less than three years of teaching experience. Both teachers and administrators have participated in relatively few professional development trainings at the district, division, and national levels. School administrators, who are slightly older than teachers, also generally have moderate levels of experience (4-6 years) and many are married.
2. Both teachers and administrators generally hold a positive attitude towards Blended Learning Modality (BLM), particularly appreciating its potential to improve health protocols and ensure safety. The highest level of agreement was on the role of BLM in enhancing health standards. However, there is some uncertainty about whether BLM can fully address all elements of the educational process, with specific concerns about its effectiveness in managing assessments and covering comprehensive educational aspects.
3. Teachers generally perceive BLM as a positive approach that can enhance course management, interaction, and overall student performance. Administrators share this view, seeing BLM as beneficial for improving student engagement and interaction within the school community. However, both groups expressed reservations about the convenience and comprehensiveness of BLM compared to traditional methods, particularly concerning the management of assignments and ensuring a thorough educational process.
4. Satisfaction with BLM is mixed among both teachers and administrators. While they

recognize the value of a comprehensive approach that integrates online, modular, TV/Radio, and face-to-face instruction, their satisfaction might be lower compared to traditional classroom settings. Despite the strong academic performance observed among students, the survey found no statistically significant relationship between teachers' or administrators' perceptions of BLM implementation and student academic performance.

5. The study revealed a weak to moderate correlation between teachers' years of experience, participation in regional in-service training, and their attitude towards BLM with their perception of BLM implementation. For administrators, weak correlations were observed between their attitude towards BLM, their participation in relevant in-service training at the division and regional levels, and their perception of BLM implementation. These findings suggest that while experience and training influence perceptions of BLM, the relationships are not strong, indicating that other factors may also play significant roles. While BLM is generally viewed positively, especially for its health and safety benefits, and potential to enhance student interaction, further investigation is necessary to determine a definitive link between BLM implementation and academic achievement. The cautious optimism expressed by both teachers and administrators suggests that with ongoing refinement and support, BLM could be more effectively integrated into the educational process.

Recommendations

Anchored on the conclusions drawn from the findings, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Both teachers (particularly younger with less experience) and administrators crave more professional development on blended learning implementation. This should include district, division, and national training programs.
2. Tailor professional development to address teachers' concerns about managing assessments and ensuring blended learning covers all educational aspects.
3. Provide training for administrators on effectively supporting teachers in implementing blended learning models.
4. Promote a comprehensive blended learning model that combines online learning, modular activities, traditional classroom instruction, and potentially TV/Radio educational programs. This aligns with the preferences of both teachers and administrators.
5. Develop clear and comprehensive guidelines for blended learning implementation to address any uncertainties about its effectiveness in covering all educational aspects.
6. Help teachers develop efficient and effective assessment strategies specifically designed for blended learning environments.

7. Create a supportive school environment where teachers feel comfortable experimenting with blended learning strategies and seeking help from colleagues and administrators.
8. Ensure blended learning models are designed to cater to the diverse needs and learning styles of students.
9. Conduct more in-depth research to establish a clearer link between blended learning implementation and student academic achievement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study prioritized the ethical treatment of all respondents. Before data collection, informed consent was secured from both teacher and school administrator respondents. This involved providing comprehensive written and verbal explanations of the research objectives, procedures, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Respondents were explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without incurring any penalty or adverse consequences. Furthermore, the confidentiality of all collected data, especially student information, was strictly maintained through rigorous measures to ensure privacy and anonymity.

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